

as 0.3 μg in 25 ml of final volume with the adjustment of pH using ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer and dil. HCl or dil. NH_4OH .

The method is advantageous because of easy preparation of the reagent, marked colour change from scarlet-red to blue-violet, immediate colour reaction, stability of the reagent and low temperature coefficient.

Experimental

The Ba-SPADNS complex and the Sr-SPADNS complex show maximum absorbance at 570 nm and 560 nm respectively using distilled water as a reference. The absorption maxima of the reagent against water for barium and strontium are 522 nm and 520 nm respectively.

The effect of pH on the absorbance was studied. The maximum absorbance was noticed at pH 10-11 for Ba and pH 8.5-9.5 for Sr respectively. Ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer, dil. HCl or dil. NH_4OH were used for varying pH. The Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.2-60 μg of Ba and 0.3-60 μg of Sr respectively. The molar absorptivities of Ba-SPADNS and Sr-SPADNS are 1.3×10^4 (at 570 nm) and 4.3×10^3 (at 560 nm) respectively. No change in optical density was noted for 72 hours for Ba-SPADNS and 4 hours for Sr-SPADNS complexes which suggests that they are sufficiently stable for quantitative determinations.

The sensitivities of the colour reactions are 0.2 μg Ba per cm^2 and 0.3 μg Sr per cm^2 (practical) respectively. The stoichiometric composition of the coloured complexes have been determined colorimetrically by adopting the "Slope Ratio Method" and "Job's method"^{5,6} which suggest a 1:1 complex for both the elements with the reagent. Nearly all the elements associated with Ba and Sr were tested to determine the behaviour with SPADNS under the optimum conditions used for Ba-SPADNS and Sr-SPADNS reactions. It has been found that 10 mg amounts of Zn, Fe, Cu, Pb, Ni, V, Nb, Sb, As, Cr, Ga, Ir, Sn, Au, Ag and W do not interfere in the determination of these elements. However, Ca, Mg and Ba in presence of Sr and Sr in presence of Ba interfere seriously.

As the absorption maxima of Ba and Sr are very close to each other, these elements can't be determined by simultaneous spectrophotometry.

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Kinetic Study of Oxidation of Aliphatic Dicarboxylic Acids by Cerium(IV) Ion in Acidic Medium

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A review of the literature shows that the oxidation of aliphatic dicarboxylic acids by cerium(IV) ion has not received much attention. Only recently a preliminary work¹⁻⁴ on the oxidation of oxalic acid, malonic acid has been carried out but the mode of attack of the acids by oxidation species from the Ce(IV) ion has not been worked out, nor the different stages involved, and the effect of $-\text{CH}_3$ group on the overall reaction rate in the process elucidated. Hence, we have undertaken a systematic kinetic study of the oxidation of aliphatic dicarboxylic acids—oxalic, malonic, succinic and glutaric acid by ceric sulphate in acidic medium. Comparative kinetic data of these studies is present in this paper which has enabled us to arrive at a suitable reaction mechanism and the effect of $-\text{CH}_3$ group for this class of reactions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either 'Analar or E. Mercks' guaranteed reagent quality. The stock solution of ceric sulphate was prepared by dissolving a known amount of it in calculated volume of sulphuric acid and diluting with double distilled water. The solutions of the reactive substances were brought to the required temperature in a thermostat, which maintained the temperature at a constant value with in $\pm 0.1^\circ$ and then rapidly mixed. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time and reaction was stopped by adding ice-cold double distilled water. The estimation of unreacted ceric(IV) was done with standard solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator.

Results

All these reactions have been found to show pseudo first order w.r.t. ceric sulphate. However, the pseudo first order rate constant generally

decreases slightly with time in any particular kinetic run. The rate of reaction in each case is also pseudo first order w.r.t. organic acid. It increases with an increase in the concentration of organic acid.

The pseudo first order behaviour of the reaction w.r.t. organic acid in each case has been confirmed by plotting $1/K$ vs. $1/[\text{Reductant}]$. The plot for each acid is a straight line which does not pass through the origin but cuts $1/K$ axis at a certain distance, giving as information about the complex formation between cerium(IV) and organic acid which is in the conformity with the mechanism postulated by us.

The rate of reaction in each case is inversely proportional to the square of the concentration of sulphuric acid. The plot of K vs. $1/[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2$ is a straight line in each case. This fact is confirmed by mechanism elucidated. The similar behaviour has been reported by Krishna and Tiwari⁶ in the oxidation of hydroxy acid by Ce(IV) ion.

The mole ratio of ceric sulphate is 2 : 1, 6 : 1, 10 : 1 and 14 : 1 with oxalic acid, malonic, succinic, and glutaric acids respectively. It is obvious that with an increase of one $-\text{CH}_2$ group in the acid, the 4 moles of ceric sulphate are more needed for the oxidation of organic acid. The overall reaction on the basis of stoichiometry may be written as below for different acids.

Energy Parameters

The various energy parameter of these reaction are recorded together in Table 1.

TABLE—1			
Reductant Acid	Energy of activation (E) in K cal.mole ⁻¹	Entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) E. U.	Free energy (ΔG^\ddagger) in K cal.mole ⁻¹
Oxalic	12.6	-35.4	22.4
Malonic	10.8	-41.8	22.3
Succinic	13.9	-37.6	25.5
Glutaric	12.4	-41.6	25.3

It is clear from the above data that the free energy of activation is of similar order of magnitude in the four cases; the energy of activation is nearly the same in all reactions except in the case of malonic acid. The value of ΔS^\ddagger is large and negative and frequency factor⁶ in each case is of the order less than 10^{10} sec^{-1} , suggests the chain mechanism involving free radical in all these four reactions.

Discussion

The final products of oxidation of malonic, succinic and glutaric acid are formic acid and CO_2 , while oxalic acid is oxidised into water and CO_2 . The formation of the products is through the complex formation between Ce(IV) and the concerned acid. The complex being unstable decomposes into acid aldehydes and Ce(III). The acid aldehydes so formed are oxidised by Ce(IV) to formic acid and CO_2 as is seen in the case of malonic acid⁷ oxidation by Ce(IV) and malic acid oxidation by quinquivalent vanadium⁸.

The general rate expression for this class of compounds by Ce(IV) adopting the mechanism of Hardwick and Robertson⁹ has been derived as :

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = k. [\text{Ce(IV)}]$$

which in the velocity equation obtained experimentally by us.

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Estimation of Crotyl and Cinnamyl Alcohols with Dichloramine-T in Partially Aqueous and Non-aqueous Media

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ORGANIC haloamines have found increasing applications as mild oxidants and analytical reagents in the estimation of compounds in solution. Dichloramine-T (N, N'-dichloro-p-toluene sulphonamide, hereinafter abbreviated as DCT) has been introduced by Jacob and Nair¹ as an oxidimetric reagent in non-aqueous and partially aqueous media and it has been used for estimating a variety of compounds such as hydroquinone², oxine³, metal oxinates³, thiols and their metal complexes^{4,5}, metal cyanides and their complexes⁶ and indigocarmine and isatin⁷. Conjugated alcohols such as crotyl alcohol and cinnamyl alcohol have a number of important applications. Crotyl alcohol finds use as a lachrymator, herbicide and soil fumigant, while cinnamyl alcohol is employed as a flavouring agent and in perfumery. In the present investigations, we have examined the behaviour of DCT towards these alcohols. While the oxidation of alcohols was found to be sluggish in 50% v/v ethanol medium, crotyl alcohol in partially aqueous medium and cinnamic alcohol solution in glacial acetic acid could be oxidized by DCT, with a two electron change. The rate was not rapid enough for a direct titration of alcohols with visual or potentiometric end point detection and hence back titration procedures were employed.

Experimental

Crotyl alcohol (Fluka, B.P. 125°, $n_D = 1.424$) was used without further purification, but the purity was checked by phthalation with phthalic anhydride in pyridine⁸. Aqueous solutions containing a definite weight of the alcohol were prepared. Cinnamyl alcohol (Naarden, corrected B.P. 256.6°) was distilled under reduced pressure and the purity

was checked⁹. Solutions of the compound in glacial acetic acid were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of the sample.

Dichloramine-T was prepared and purified by the method of Jacob and Nair¹. An approximately decinormal solution of the oxidant in glacial acetic acid (containing 10% v/v acetic anhydride) was prepared and standardized by the iodometric method¹.

Preliminary Studies :

Known volumes of alcohol solution were added to a known excess of decinormal DCT solution in an iodine flask. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature with occasional shaking, for different intervals of time. About 10 ml of 20% KI solution were then added and the liberated iodine was titrated against sodium thiosulphate solution. A blank titration was carried out with the same volume of DCT. The time required for the stoichiometric oxidation of crotyl and cinnamic alcohols by DCT was calculated. Table 1 shows the extent

TABLE 1—EXTENT OF OXIDATION OF CROTYL AND CINNAMIC ALCOHOLS WITH DICHLORAMINE-T

Time (minutes)	Equivalents of DCT consumed $\times 10^3$	Equivalents of DCT consumed / Equivalents of alcohol taken
<i>Crotyl alcohol</i>		
5	0.2951	1.77
10	0.3165	1.89
20	0.3272	1.96
30	0.3307	1.98
45	0.3343	2.00
60	0.3343	2.00
18 hrs.	0.3360	2.01
<i>Cinnamic alcohol</i>		
10	0.1840	1.11
20	0.1952	1.61
30	0.2105	1.74
45	0.2258	1.87
60	0.2325	1.93
70	0.2343	1.95
90	0.2418	2.00
120	0.2418	2.00
16 hrs.	0.2433	2.01

Crotyl alcohol taken : 0.1671 m mole.

DCT taken : 0.25 m mole.

Cinnamic alcohol taken : 0.1211 m mole.

DCT taken : 0.41 m mole.

of oxidation of the alcohols with DCT. It is seen that stoichiometric oxidation of crotyl alcohol with a two electron change takes place in about 45 minutes while cinnamic alcohol requires 90 minutes in the concentration range used.

Recommended Procedure :

An aliquot of alcohol solution (2-36 mg) was added to a known excess of DCT (~ 0.40 m mole) in an iodine flask at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ$). The reaction mixture was shaken and kept aside for 45 and 90 minutes respectively for crotyl and cinnamic

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